

PREDICTING FINANCIAL DISTRESS OF NIGERIAN ELECTRICITY DISTRIBUTION COMPANIES USING THE ALTMAN Z-SCORE MODEL

CELESTINE CHUKWUTEM EBOGBUE^{1*}, AHMAD BUKOLA UTHMAN² and LUCKY OTSOGE ONMONYA³

^{1,2,3}Department of Accounting, Nile University of Nigeria, Abuja.

ORCID: ¹<https://orcid.org/0009-0008-6524-9102>(*Corresponding Author),

²<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-4272-5574>, ³<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-1081-270X>

Abstract

The study examines the prediction of financial distress of Nigerian electricity distribution companies using the Altman Z-score model. Ex post facto research design was adopted for the study to assess the effectiveness and adequacy of the independent variables(working capital to total assets, retained earnings to total assets, earnings before interest and tax to total assets, market value of book value of equity to total liabilities and sales to total assets) of the Altman Z-Score model in influencing the Z-score result, regardless of the direction it is skewed, is a determinant of whether a firm could be classified as being engaged in fraudulent financial statement practices or not. Centred on the Nigerian Electricity Distribution Companies (DisCos), the study's sample comprises the financial statements of the 11 successor companies for the period from 2013 to 2023, available on their respective websites. A panel regression model was used to test the hypotheses, as the findings indicated that the Altman Z-score model could effectively predict financial failure among the Nigerian Electricity Distribution Companies (DisCos). Additionally, the model shows a significant relationship between the Altman Z-score and the model's independent variables, and between these variables and the prediction of failures of the Nigerian Electricity Distribution Companies (DisCos). In conclusion, the study proved that the Altman Z-score model could reliably and efficiently predict and detect financial distress in organisations and recommended its use to future-proof DisCos' operational efficiency and survival prospects. Given its limitations, stakeholders could make more informed decisions and take proactive measures to mitigate financial distress.

Keywords: DisCo, Electricity, Prediction, Model, Altman Z-Score, Distress, Bankruptcy.

1. INTRODUCTION

The Nigerian power sector is a topic of discussion in both local and international contexts due to its role in Nigeria's and Africa's economic development. Every economic activity and industrial development rides on the backbone of the power distribution companies (DisCos) in Nigeria. This, therefore, assumes that their operational efficiencies oil the engines of development in the economy.

The sector (particularly distribution) has become so vulnerable to economic instability due to mediocre policy implementation, inadequate distribution infrastructure, exchange rate volatility, and exogenous factors affecting the country's revenue base, making it imperative to predict the financial distress of electricity distribution companies in Nigeria. This is because the sector's failure to maintain financial system stability not only threatens its sustainability but also strains the overall economy.

Electric power activities began in Nigeria in 1898 (Thomas et al., 2023), particularly in Lagos, the country's commercial nerve centre. In 1923, a 2 MW power generation system was installed by local miners in Kwali, Abuja, and was subsequently followed by another installation of a 25 MW hydroelectric power generating system by the Nigerian Electricity Supply Company (NESCO) in Jos in 1929 (Onyegbule, 2023) to aid the mining activities in these areas. Subsequently, in 1969, the African Timber and Plywood (AT&P) had commenced power generation in Ogorode, Sapele (Aideyan, 2023).

Between 1950 and 1969, there were different transformation phases in the power sector in Nigeria, ranging from the Power Works Department (PWD) in Lagos, the Electricity Corporation of Nigeria (ECN), to the building of the first Transmission lines in 1961 (Abanihi et al., 2018), and the construction and commissioning of the Kainji Dam in 1969. The National Electric Power Authority (NEPA) came in 1972 and was transformed into the Power Holding Company of Nigeria (PHCN) in 1995 (Ajumogobia & Okeke, 2015). In 2005, the Electric Power Sector Reform Act (EPSRA) was enacted to prepare for the sector's unbundling and privatisation, which commenced in 2013 with six successor power plants by five generating companies (GenCos), one transmission company (TCN), and eleven distribution companies (DisCos). Currently, over 23 GenCos and 12 DisCos operate in the country under the regulatory purview of the Nigerian Electricity Regulatory Commission (NERC).

With recent developments in Nigeria's power sector and government policies promoting efficiency in power generation and distribution, assessing the financial health of Nigeria's electricity distribution companies is highly relevant. DisCos' successful operations and existence are continually challenged by prevailing economic conditions, which continue to make industry operations very challenging. The challenges of galloping inflation, exchange rate fluctuations and floating, gas price volatility, and restricted access to credit facilities have major impediments to DisCos' successful operations. This research focuses on the electricity sector, a key driver of Nigeria's economic development, by examining the implications of financial distress among the DisCos using the financial statements covering 2013–2023. As tools used by potential investors to assess the possibility of investing in an organisation, financial statements must follow recognised reporting standards (Siregar et al., 2023) in their presentation and serve as a guide to prospective and potential shareholders in making investment decisions (Gbadebo et al., 2023).

Predicting failure in corporate organisations involves using financial and analytical models to identify early warning signals of bankruptcy or financial distress in firms (Braunsberger & Aschauer, 2025). The predictions are significant towards curtailing economic losses affecting investors, lenders, regulators, employees, and suppliers. Historically, failure prediction evolved from simple financial ratio analysis to quantitative predictive models, beginning with major studies by Beaver (1966) and Altman (1968). Over time, researchers developed increasingly sophisticated models to improve prediction accuracy. A failed or distressed organisation has several negative implications, including financial losses, reputational damage from media reports, and other consequences that are often difficult to erase (Burnaby et al., 2011), with losses increasing in magnitude (Okaro et al., 2013), as well as bankruptcy reports and

organisational winding-up. Enron and the subsequent bankruptcy of Arthur Andersen, an international accounting firm, were typical examples.

MacCarthy (2017) revealed that distress, bankruptcy, and fraud are inseparable twins, purposefully exhibited by companies under pressure from the board or management to present a picture of good performance to potential investors and shareholders. The Nigerian power sector positions itself as an easy target. DisCos' operations are often susceptible to distress due to the target and regulatory framework, and the environment of meeting the required customers' and grid requirements. A major gap in the chain of events in their operations is electricity theft, which strains their ability to meet revenue requirements, and these have not been quantified in the annual financial statements.

The research, therefore, focuses on using the Z-score model to determine financial distress of the Nigerian Electricity Distribution Companies (DisCos), utilising data from audited financial statements for 2013–2023, where available. Using the Z-score model (rather than traditional ratios), the researchers intend to show possible distress symptoms in the DisCos using their audited financial statements, for the benefit of current and potential investors, not just in the power sector but also in other industries.

The research is broken down into five sections. Section 2 will discuss the relevant literature on the concept of financial distress, the Altman Z-score prediction model, an important tool for predicting the potential existence of an organisation (Jean et al., 2021), and the formulation of the study hypothesis based on the data collated for this research. Section 3 will focus on the study's methods and material, while the presentation of results from the analysed data and findings will be discussed in Section 4. The study's conclusions and recommendations will be presented in Section 5.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

In financial reporting, financial distress poses a "peril to the sustainability" of organisations and challenges the trust of current and potential investors in companies (Miharsi et al., 2024), and in most cases, regarded as fraud. Though not a misstatement, it is a resulting effect from deliberately misstating facts in financial reporting for an unlawful usage or undue benefit derived from assets that belong to another person (Saleh et al., 2021). According to Teja (2025), financial distress is the likelihood that a company will not meet its obligations whenever they fall due. This signifies the inability to meet accrued liabilities, either due to insufficient income or otherwise.

The situation could be temporary; however, if it lasts for a protracted period, it could result in insolvency, bankruptcy, and, subsequently, liquidation. A challenging condition of this type, when experienced by a company, could drastically reduce the market value, as suppliers of goods and services avoid delivery without payment (Teja, 2025). In this condition, companies are unable to generate revenue to offset current obligations (Garcia & Esquivel, 2024). Financial distress is a term used to describe the condition of a company that is experiencing financial difficulties (Cındık & Armutlulu, 2021)

The gravity of information misrepresentation in financial statements has necessitated the use of various early-detection tools or models, including the Altman Z-Score and others, each with its own strengths and limitations (Miharsi et al., 2024). However, with the misrepresentation of facts, it becomes possible to predict alternatives and expose the basis of unprincipled infections that could, over time, become a reality, driven by the possibility of failure (Pedneault et al., 2012; Hossain, 2020).

Braunsberger and Aschauer (2025) compared the Altman Z-score through a machine-learning lens and its implications for corporate failure prediction. Focused on technological features, organisational readiness, environmental pressure and user perceptions, the literature review indicated that with a technology acceptance Model, the Altman Z-score models offer simplicity, interpretability and low-cost techniques that suit firms with limited analytical resources, indicating when it is appropriate to adopt the model in making corporate predictions, setting an agenda for long-horizon forecasting, explainable artificial intelligence and context-specific model design for ML. According to the researchers, insights from the Z-score enable management to make choices about failure prediction tools that align with their organisation's strategic objectives and implementation capacity. These choices are premised on understanding the unique features of each industry, market dynamics, and the model's adaptability (Idris & Dzugwah, 2024).

In failure prediction and fraud detection, financial analysts and auditors analyse financial statements using predictive and detection models to benefit their clients (Rasa & Zivile, 2015). In most cases, traditional financial ratios, which remain relevant today, are used for these activities across jurisdictions, despite their perceived limitations. This prompts the use of the Altman Z-Score model, as presented herein, to predict and identify potential failures or bankruptcies of organisations within the next two years (Saleh et al., 2021).

The Altman Z-score – a bankruptcy model = is a powerful warning tool for firms' operations, serving as a measurable control tool for the financial status of a company that is experiencing financial distress (Garcia & Esquivel, 2024). In other words, the Altman Z-Score is used as a predictive model to assess a company's likelihood of bankruptcy, ensuring that the firm is vigilant in its financial dealings, activities, and reporting techniques to avoid fraudulent practices that could harm its reputation within the league of firms, as investors' decisions may be influenced. To predict the failure probability of Indian steel companies, Singh and Singla (2023) employed regression analysis using the Z-score model and found that size is inversely related to failure probability, but they did not assert that the size might be positively correlated with fraudulent financial statement reporting.

First proposed by Professor Edward Altman in 1968, the model is a regression-based empirical version for predicting bankruptcy using a firm's annual audited financial statements. The model focuses on predicting the possible bankruptcy of manufacturing organisations, using statistical modelling. MacCarthy (2017) stated that the model's ability to predict a "very high degree" probability of failure relies on its capacity to detect possible financial recklessness of organisations. This not only relates to a single market, but also to the proper understanding of financial distress in both developed and emerging markets, with good

classification of the model's variables into five independent variables and providing the chances to forecast the possibilities of a firm going bankrupt in future (Kamaluddin et al., 2024).

The model has become a viable predictive tool for failure and is commonly used to assess a company's insolvency level (Kulkarni & Kothari, 2020). With the challenges of the 21st century increasingly impacting organisational survival, firms strive to remain consistently profitable in their operations, under pressure to improve and maintain outstanding credibility to sustain relevance and avoid unnecessary bankruptcy and takeover challenges amid competition (Ranjbar & Amanollahi, 2018). The model utilises a 5-variable analysis that encompasses all aspects of the financial statement to measure a firm's performance or competence. Using 66 firms (33 failed and 33 solvent) with assets exceeding \$1 million, the model developed a score to predict corporate failures. This research presents the components in Figure 1 below, illustrating the independent and dependent variables of Altman's Z-score model, with the dependent variables as a proxy for financial distress.

Figure 1: Research Framework

$$Z = 1.2X_1 + 1.4X_2 + 3.3X_3 + 0.6X_4 + 0.99X_5$$

Decision criterion: >2.99 (Safe Zone), $1.81 < Z < 2.99$ (Grey Zone), and <1.81 (Distress Zone).

While corroborating Garcia and Esquivel (2024), Singh and Singla (2023) stated that the model is developed to alert firms of their slide into bankruptcy. Adopting the Z-score and P-score in a study of construction companies in Latvia, Liodorova and Voronova (2019), despite the challenge of large data gathering from those firms that are on “the verge insolvency and having signs of fraud due to information confidentiality”, realised a high accuracy level of the models of above 80% in its bankruptcy and fraud predictions in the sector. The study's findings have demonstrated the consistency of the Altman Z-Score model not only in predicting bankruptcy but also in detecting financial malfeasance, considered an encouraging factor for fraudulent reporting.

In a study of metal and mineral industrial companies listed on the Indonesian Stock Exchange (BEI) during 2020-2021, Garcia and Esquivel (2024) used the Altman Z-score model to predict bankruptcy. Using purposive sampling techniques, data were derived from 7 companies for the period. The results from the research categorised 5 companies in the safe zone, 1 in the grey zone, and 1 in the distress zone. The categorisation presents a forecast prediction of organisations in a possible bankruptcy region and a pointer to adopting strategies that could save the companies from liquidation. Garcia and Esquivel's (2024) study, following the classification of the companies, shows improvements in the 2021 annual audited financial statements of the companies.

In their study of the exposures of construction companies in Latvia, Liodorova and Voronova (2019) proposed that the Altman Z-score model can accurately predict more than 80% of financial distress in the financial statements. Miharsi et al. (2024) in a contemporary literature review stated that the "Altman Z-Score, synthesising financial ratios, has demonstrated efficacy in discerning fraud" and financial distress.

Accordingly, the model demonstrates adaptability in evaluating different companies and sectoral risks related to financial statement manipulations, utilising various ratios, including liquidity, profitability, leverage, solvency, and productivity, to assess the robustness of a company's financial performance (Kukreja et al., 2020). The Z-score model is acknowledged for its capacity to mitigate certain shortcomings of financial ratios while yielding highly dependable results for measuring organisational financial performance, highlighting activities that are fraudulently projective in nature (Miharsi et al., 2024).

Using information from companies' audited financial statements, the model employs a linear combination of independent variables to assess companies' financial health. MacCarthy (2017), however, noted that, irrespective of the model's near perfection, the results are impacted either by geographical regions or industries, as its application may not be generally applicable to all sectors due to differing characteristics, based on the assumptions of the accuracy of the financial ratios obtained from the audited financial statements. This assumption overlooks the possibility that companies in distress could manipulate their financial reports to show superior performance.

3. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Financial Distress and Bankruptcy

Theories of financial distress and bankruptcy are closely linked, as financial failure often results in bankruptcy and liquidation. Amaniyah et al. (2025) opined that financial distress arises from a company's operational errors, including but not limited to inappropriate planning, wrong judgments, and weaknesses in various functionalities of the company.

Financial ratios are a good means of detecting potential signs of distress in an organisation, and they can be derived from companies audited financial statements. These signs usually exist long before an organisation can be declared bankrupt (Amaniyah et al., 2025).

Researchers use financial ratio analysis to anticipate potential company bankruptcy in organisations. The earliest bankruptcy prediction can be traced back to 1932, with Fitzpatrick's analysis of financial ratios of 20 companies to distinguish failing from healthy companies, thereby forming a prediction model (Amaniyah et al., 2025). The process used macroeconomic factors as predictors of financial distress.

Detzer and Herr (2014) categorised 3 financial-crisis models, all of which emphasise that the monetary sphere is the primary outcome of distress. The categorisations are the neoclassical theory, the monetary production theory, and the economic model approach. While the neoclassical model sees financial crises as a disturbing factor in stable operations and the economy, the monetary production model understands the role of uncertainties in the operation of both the economy and the industry and the resultant effects on the organisation's vision. The economic model understands the implications of endogenous and exogenous factors for the monetary production of uncertainty and how this affects the organisation's results.

4. EMPIRICAL REVIEW

Empirically, this study examines the appropriateness, relevance and efficiency of the Altman Z-score model in the Nigerian Electricity Distribution sector, by assessing the model's capacity to account for the various economic and financial challenges peculiar to the distribution companies. The model is used to ascertain the relationships between the independent variables embedded in the Z-score and issues of financial distress or insolvency, and to correlate these relationships to enhance ethical and prudent management of resources within the DisCos. This study contributes to knowledge on the sustainability and efficiency of the Nigerian power sector reform, a critical research area.

DisCos are grappling with various operational and financial challenges, including electricity tariffs. Inadequate infrastructure, energy theft, and low collection rates are among the numerous challenges. All these add up to the economic challenges the Discos are encountering. Understanding the links between these economic challenges and sectoral challenges, and modelling the probability of distress, is vital for the industry's stakeholders. Enhanced predictive accuracy will guarantee that the right investments are made at the right time, regulatory actions are timely, and managerial responses are appropriate. The electricity sector is a critical component of any economy's development, and threats to its stability must be addressed promptly.

Given concerns over the intensifying financial complaints of the DisCos between 2014 and 2023, this research utilises a proven distress prediction model, the Altman Z-Score, to analyse the inherent failure risks using audited financial statements. Prepared with the utmost care to minimise errors, financial statements ensure that information is presented in a true, fair and accurate manner (Rasa & Zivile, 2015), thereby guarding informed decisions or judgements about the company. However, this is not enough to prevent distress, given the pressures on management and the tendency to take undue advantage of opportunities, including manipulating figures to show better performance or concealing losses.

While adopting the use of models in studying the possibilities of fraudulent financial reporting in the Jordanian manufacturing environment, Saleh et al. (2021) utilised the Z-score and F-score models in their research study with data from 2015 to 2019 (5 years), which confirmed the validity and accuracy of these models in predicting and detecting financial distress within organisations. The research utilises a multiple regression model to evaluate various fraud theories and the factors contributing to their perpetration. In a similar study, Kukreja et al. (2020) utilised the Beneish M-score and Altman Z-score as indicators of corporate fraud and corporate failures using Comscore Inc.'s financial statements (2012-2018), with the objective to predict early warning signs of fraud and financial distress that could lead to the company's failure. The study found the Altman Z-score to be highly effective at predicting early signs of fraudulent activity in an organisation's financial statement reporting.

Acting from this and the findings of Braunsberger and Aschauer (2025), this research intends to answer the following research hypothesis:

H₁: The Altman Z-score model could not effectively predict financial distress in the Nigerian Electricity Distribution Companies (DisCos) from the audited financial statements.

The dependent variables, or the five accounting ratios of the Z-score model, evaluate a company's liquidity and capacity to meet its financial commitments (Pratiwi et al., 2022), financial distress in terms of profitability and productivity (Toly et al., 2020), identify earnings falsifications, show the efficacy of debt repayment to win over stakeholders (Pratiwi et al., 2022), and determine the utilisation of total assets to create sales (Maccarthy, 2017; Toly et al., 2020; Pratiwi et al., 2022). The results from these studies and the arguments on the geographical effects of the application of the Altman Z-score model resulted in the second hypothesis for the study using the Altman Z-score for selected companies in Nigeria:

H₂: There is no significant correlation between the independent variables of the Altman Z-score model in predicting financial distress in the Nigerian Electricity Distribution Companies (DisCos) using the audited financial statements.

The efficacy of the Altman Z-score in predicting financial distress from financial statements lies in its ability to determine whether an organisation's operational activities fall within the safe or grey zone, thereby indicating susceptibility to bankruptcy. Africa, as a test case in recent research, has been overlooked due to inadequate information in audited financial statements, insufficient disclosures and reporting frameworks, a lack of resources, and the absence of legal enforcement (Alastair et al., 2023; Nyakiarimi, 2022; Okiro & Otiso, 2021).

5. METHODOLOGY

This study utilises an ex post facto research design to assess the effectiveness and adequacy of the independent variables of the Altman Z-Score model in influencing the Z-score result, regardless of the direction of skewness, which is a determinant of whether a firm can be classified as safe, grey, or distressed. This section presents the empirical results from the

statistical analysis conducted in Stata, which evaluates the effectiveness of the Altman Z-score model in predicting financial distress among DisCos, using audited financial statements from 2013 to 2023, available on their respective websites. The section analyses the descriptive statistics, normality tests, correlation analyses, regression results, and the summary classification of financial distress for the companies studied.

6. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Descriptive Statistics

Table 1: Descriptive Statistics

	(1)			
	mean	sd	min	max
zscore	.0341752	4.5353	-11.38892	28.69554
X1	-.5859687	.7201594	-3.302274	.1517855
X2	-.2508238	.8623716	-3.259468	1.90823
X3	-.0791802	.4869005	-1.068327	3.036461
X4	1.266254	4.947505	-.7631295	46.26841
X5	.5900329	.3670823	.1631245	3.450003
N	121			

Table 1 discusses the components of the Altman model and the financial ratios used in the model, and presents them in a descriptive statistics format. In the Table, the variables include working capital to total assets (X1), retained earnings to total assets (X2), earnings before interest and taxes to total assets (X3), market value of equity to total liabilities (X4), and sales to total assets (X5). However, since DisCos have no market value of equity, the book value was used to calculate the Z-score.

From Table 1 above, the mean Altman Z-score is 0.034, with a standard deviation of 4.535, indicating significant variation in the DisCos financial conditions. The mean Z-score is substantially lower than the Altman distress threshold of 1.81, meaning that, realistically, on average, the electricity distribution companies operated within the financial distress zone during the study period. This could have been made possible by the several interventions by the Federal Government of Nigeria to ensure the DisCos do not fizzle out of operations. However, the minimum Z-score of -11.3889 suggests acute severe financial distress for some DisCos, while the maximum Z-score of 28.6955 indicates extremely strong financial distress in certain years. The range between the minimum and maximum values indicates considerable heterogeneity in the firms' financial conditions.

Taken together, the descriptive statistics suggest that most of the DisCos faced severe financial challenges during the study period in terms of liquidity, profitability and retained profit.

Table 2: Shapiro-Wilk Normality Test

Variable	Obs	W	V	z	Prob>z
zscore	121	0.830	16.451	6.277	0.000

Table 2 presents the Shapiro–Wilk test for normality of the Z-score variable. The test statistic, W, is 0.830, and the p-value is 0.000, which is <0.05, indicating statistical significance at the 5% level.

The null hypothesis of the Shapiro–Wilk test assumes that all the variables are normally distributed. Since the p-value is less than 0.05, the null hypothesis is rejected, indicating that the Z-score data are not normally distributed. The non-normal distribution of financial ratios is consistent with findings in financial distress literature, where firm-level financial data often display skewness and kurtosis due to the presence of extreme financial conditions, operational inefficiencies, or industry-specific shocks, and justifies the application of Spearman's rank correlation in the analysis, which does not assume normal distribution.

Table 3: Spearman Rank Correlation Matrix

Variables	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
(1) zscore	1.000					
(2) X1	0.844	1.000				
(3) X2	0.813	0.737	1.000			
(4) X3	0.520	0.375	0.240	1.000		
(5) X4	0.826	0.881	0.792	0.198	1.000	
(5) X4	0.826	0.881	0.792	0.198	1.000	(5) X4
Spearman rho = -0.183						

Table 3 is the Spearman rank correlation matrix of the Altman Z-score and its independent variables. The output shows strong positive correlations between the Z-score and several independent variables, demonstrating the relationship between the Z-score and these variables, and the relevance of the predictors to financial distress.

X1 of 0.844 indicates a strong positive relationship between liquidity and financial stability, and a correlation with the Z-score; X2 of 0.813 shows a correlation with the Z-score and suggests a strong influence of the retained earnings on the DisCos financial health status. Profitability and financial stability show a moderate positive correlation with the Z-score (X3), with a correlation coefficient of 0.520.

The correlation between Z-score and X4 is 0.826, suggesting that leverage structure significantly influences the Z-score. Between Z-score and X5, the correlation of 0.030 indicates a weak negative relationship between asset turnover and financial stability. Further to the above, the correlation matrix equally portrays relationships among the independent variables of the Altman Z-score model. From Table 3 above, X1 and X4 show a high correlation of 0.881, suggesting interdependence between liquidity and leverage measures.

Table 4: Panel OLS Regression Results

	(1) zscore
X1	1.200 (.)
X2	1.400 (.)
X3	3.300 (.)
X4	0.600 (.)
X5	1.000 (.)
_cons	-4.58e-08 (.)
N	121

Standard errors in parentheses

* p<0.10, ** p<0.05, *** p<0.01

To examine the relationship between the Altman Z-score and its financial ratio components, Table 4 presents the panel ordinary least squares (OLS) regression results.

The X1 to X5 regression coefficients, as indicated in Table 4 above, correspond exactly to the Altman Z-score formula. These coefficients reflect the structural weights assigned by Altman from the original Z-score model. However, the model does not estimate new coefficients; it simply reconstructs the Z-score formula and reproduces the predetermined weights.

The absence of standard errors and significance statistics indicates that the regression did not estimate relationships; it reconstructed the composite index. Therefore, while the regression confirms the mathematical construction of the Z-score, it does not provide statistical evidence of predictive effectiveness.

Table 5: Summarised Results of Altman Z-score Analysis

Company	Distress	Grey Zone	Safe
1	2014-2023		2013
2	2013-2023		2013
3	2016-2018, 2022-2023	2015, 2019-2021	2013-2014
4	2015-2019, 2021-2023	2014, 2020	2013
5	2016-2023	2013-2015	
6	2015-2023	2014	2013
7	2015-2023	2014	2013
8	2013, 2015-2023		2014
9	2016-2023	2015	2013-2014
10	2014-2016	2017	2013, 2018-2023
11	2013, 2015-2020, 2022-2023	2014, 2021	

Table 5 above summarises the DisCos' performance classifications based on the Altman Z-score analysis, grouping them into distress, grey, and safe zones in the study period. The results indicated that, except for a few DisCos, almost all the firms are financially distressed and require urgent intervention.

The transition to the safe zones indicates financial stability only for the period in question and does not imply the probability of remaining stable. These findings reflect the broader structural problems within the Nigerian electricity distribution subsector. Reports indicate that several

electricity companies face severe liquidity constraints, debt obligations, and operational inefficiencies. Furthermore, industry reports indicate that the sector suffers from high technical losses, poor revenue collection, and regulatory challenges. These structural issues explain the persistent financial distress observed in the Z-Score analysis.

Hypothesis Testing

Hypothesis One (H1)

H1: The Altman Z-score model could not effectively predict financial distress in the Nigerian Electricity Distribution Companies (DisCos).

The descriptive statistics (Table 1) and classification results (Table 5) indicate that most DisCos remained in the distress zone for the study period. Even though the model had correctly identified financial weakness in the sector, the regression analysis failed to provide statistical evidence of predictive accuracy because the coefficients are predetermined rather than estimated. Based on this, even if the Z-score reflects financial distress, it does not provide statistically predictive estimates specific to the industry's subsector.

Decision: Based on the above, we fail to reject the hypothesis that the Altman Z-score model does not effectively predict financial distress, specifically within the Nigerian DisCos, as it ordinarily reproduces the predetermined formula without industry-specific calibration.

Hypothesis Two (H2)

H2: There is no significant correlation between the independent variables of the Altman Z-score model in predicting financial distress in the Nigerian Electricity Distribution Companies.

The Spearman's correlation matrix indicates strong relationships between the Z-score and several independent variables, particularly X1 (0.844), X2 (0.813), and X4 (0.826), proving the significant influence of liquidity, retained earnings, and leverage ratios on the financial distress indicator.

The correlation results, therefore, contradict the null hypothesis.

Decision: Based on the above, we reject the hypothesis that there is no significant correlation between the Altman Z-score components in predicting financial distress in the Nigerian DisCos.

7. CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Having analysed the financial condition of Nigerian DisCos using the Altman Z-Score model, the results indicate widespread financial distress across the DisCos, with most of the firms categorised as distressed during the study period.

The findings equally reveal significant relationships between independent variables and the Altman Z-score, supporting the relevance of the model's components (Braunsberger & Aschauer, 2025; MacCarthy, 2017).

However, the model's predictive effectiveness appears limited due to structural differences between the DisCos and the industries for which it was originally designed, consistent with MacCarthy (2017). For the Nigerian electricity sector reform, the findings above have serious policy implications.

First, the financial distress of distribution companies underscores the urgency of improved financial reform, formulation of specific industry reporting standards, and regulatory oversight. The Nigerian Electricity Regulatory Commission (NERC) and the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) should strengthen financial monitoring frameworks to sustain the DisCo.

Second, DisCos must make sacrifices to improve their revenue collection efficiency, as studies have shown that they suffer substantial losses due to technical inefficiencies, poor billing systems mechanisms, and inadequate infrastructural investments in the network.

Third, the DisCos still face the tariff's non-cost-reflectivity. It is necessary to reform the pricing mechanism of the DisCos to ensure tariff's cost-reflectivity, thereby suspending the subsidy. The inability of DisCos to recover operational costs with reasonable returns on investments has been identified as a major factor contributing to financial instability (Onyegbule, 2023).

Reducing the aggregate technical and commercial losses would require sufficient investment in infrastructure and smart metering technologies. The tariff has been provided to allow for returns on such investments (Obiora et al, 2024). Also, DisCos should align with the Federal Government's various metering investment programmes.

Finally, policymakers should consider developing sector-specific financial distress models tailored to the industry's unique characteristics.

STATA OUTPUT

```
_____ (R)
 /_/_ /_/_ /_/_ /_/_ /_/_
/_/_ /_/_ /_/_ /_/_ /_/_ 14.0
Statistics/Data Analysis
```

MP - Parallel Edition

Copyright 1985-2015 StataCorp LP
StataCorp
4905 Lakeway Drive
College Station, Texas 77845 USA
800-STATA-PC <http://www.stata.com>
979-696-4600 stata@stata.com
979-696-4601 (fax)

firmid	year	sales	currentassets	totalassets	currentliabilities	longtermdebt	totalliabilities	retainedearnings	marketvalueequity	ebit	workingcapital	X1	X2	X3	X4	X5	zscore	zone
1	2013	36,025,798.00	7,203,455.00	96,028,465.00	10,234,247.00	-	10,234,247.00	85,794,218.00	13,367,510.00	(3,030,782.00)	(3,030,782.00)	0.03	0.89	0.14	8.38	3.38	6.16	Safe
1	2014	48,097,381.00	16,630,212.00	105,500,000.00	11,280,923.00	1,125,880.00	12,406,803.00	92,093,197.00	13,367,510.00	13,367,510.00	(2,600,000.00)	0.21	0.46	(0.23)	1.49	0.46	0.06	Distress
1	2015	62,534,676.00	26,336,636.00	105,500,000.00	71,336,985.00	1,720,900.00	73,057,885.00	32,466,115.00	17,945,595.00	36,428,448.00	(38,896,830.00)	(0.41)	0.16	(0.36)	0.30	0.57	(0.57)	Distress
1	2016	61,147,937.00	33,074,288.00	117,200,000.00	126,700,000.00	1,549,884.00	128,250,000.00	(23,632,325.00)	(11,041,689.00)	(35,054,319.00)	(93,600,000.00)	(0.68)	(0.28)	(0.30)	(0.09)	0.52	(1.35)	Distress
1	2017	65,715,312.00	28,069,553.00	120,100,000.00	201,300,000.00	4,983,511.00	206,300,000.00	(105,600,000.00)	(86,804,804.00)	(48,987,828.00)	(173,000,000.00)	(1.44)	(0.88)	(0.41)	(0.42)	0.55	(4.01)	Distress
1	2018	62,220,731.00	57,199,466.00	169,900,000.00	269,300,000.00	29,404,113.00	298,700,000.00	(172,700,000.00)	(128,800,000.00)	(61,256,673.00)	(212,000,000.00)	(1.25)	(1.02)	(0.36)	(0.43)	0.48	(3.89)	Distress
1	2019	256,000,000.00	50,860,754.00	166,200,000.00	145,400,000.00	25,378,420.00	170,800,000.00	(48,543,138.00)	(4,570,597.00)	131,800,000.00	(94,500,000.00)	(0.57)	(0.29)	0.79	(0.03)	1.54	0.30	Safe
1	2020	133,400,000.00	58,236,219.00	176,700,000.00	174,000,000.00	20,967,809.00	194,900,000.00	(65,176,882.00)	(18,249,684.00)	(6,704,860.00)	(115,000,000.00)	(0.65)	(0.37)	(0.04)	(0.09)	0.76	(0.72)	Distress
1	2021	165,300,000.00	85,029,552.00	271,900,000.00	195,800,000.00	34,046,984.00	229,800,000.00	(58,850,974.00)	42,007,802.00	(924,771.00)	(111,000,000.00)	(0.41)	(0.22)	(0.00)	0.18	0.61	(0.09)	Distress
1	2022	148,500,000.00	96,845,749.00	284,100,000.00	207,600,000.00	43,449,757.00	251,000,000.00	(66,110,021.00)	32,056,450.00	1,535,285.00	(111,000,000.00)	(0.38)	(0.28)	0.03	0.13	0.52	(0.09)	Distress
1	2023	250,500,000.00	169,300,000.00	380,800,000.00	282,200,000.00	44,321,674.00	326,500,000.00	(65,651,916.00)	54,276,362.00	20,943,357.00	(113,000,000.00)	(0.30)	0.17	0.05	0.17	0.66	0.34	Distress
2	2013	38,587,423.00	6,041,831.00	40,446,176.00	8,440,788.00	11,856,359.00	20,297,147.00	1,883,275.00	20,149,029.00	(16,186,703.00)	(2,398,957.00)	(0.06)	(0.05)	(0.40)	0.99	0.95	0.09	Distress
2	2014	39,225,587.00	16,437,759.00	49,478,400.00	31,660,882.00	6,569,845.00	38,230,727.00	11,242,313.00	11,247,313.00	(6,683,871.00)	(15,200,000.00)	(0.31)	0.23	(0.14)	0.29	0.79	0.47	Distress
2	2015	37,047,417.00	28,283,907.00	61,634,988.00	50,102,560.00	4,677,535.00	54,780,095.00	6,849,873.00	6,849,873.00	(3,281,738.00)	(21,800,000.00)	(0.35)	0.11	(0.05)	(0.13)	0.60	(0.23)	Distress
2	2016	50,571,893.00	49,237,350.00	88,937,496.00	71,289,182.00	18,232,968.00	89,521,150.00	(4,775,482.00)	(594,184.00)	(6,843,851.00)	(22,100,000.00)	(0.25)	(0.08)	(0.08)	(0.01)	0.57	(0.46)	Distress
2	2017	61,734,436.00	69,489,453.00	201,800,000.00	119,800,000.00	28,632,320.00	148,400,000.00	(50,304,753.00)	(11,484,970.00)	(50,304,753.00)	(50,304,753.00)	(0.25)	(0.05)	(0.06)	0.36	0.31	(0.03)	Distress
2	2018	70,885,981.00	21,238,777.00	165,100,000.00	169,500,000.00	20,568,037.00	190,000,000.00	(84,345,126.00)	(24,983,982.00)	(35,544,858.00)	(148,000,000.00)	(0.90)	(0.51)	(0.22)	(0.13)	0.43	(2.15)	Distress
2	2019	66,282,970.00	143,000,000.00	279,800,000.00	233,300,000.00	21,538,104.00	254,800,000.00	(31,281,874.00)	24,973,477.00	81,798,314.00	(90,200,000.00)	(0.32)	(0.11)	0.29	0.10	0.24	0.72	Distress
2	2020	79,098,862.00	197,400,000.00	353,000,000.00	308,900,000.00	17,539,894.00	326,500,000.00	(26,423,759.00)	26,758,283.00	(1,260,429.00)	(112,000,000.00)	(0.32)	(0.07)	(0.00)	0.08	0.22	(0.22)	Distress
2	2021	58,474,306.00	203,300,000.00	377,500,000.00	305,400,000.00	37,894,156.00	343,300,000.00	(23,216,583.00)	34,161,568.00	(1,812,008.00)	(105,000,000.00)	(0.28)	(0.06)	(0.00)	0.10	0.26	(0.12)	Distress
2	2022	110,000,000.00	227,200,000.00	434,900,000.00	360,200,000.00	70,028,109.00	430,300,000.00	(62,933,598.00)	4,824,035.00	(11,986,612.00)	(133,000,000.00)	(0.31)	(0.12)	(0.03)	0.01	0.25	(0.37)	Distress
2	2023	120,300,000.00	257,100,000.00	461,000,000.00	316,500,000.00	79,693,647.00	396,200,000.00	(7,265,633.00)	64,823,266.00	74,197,053.00	(59,400,000.00)	(0.13)	0.02	0.16	0.16	0.26	0.76	Distress
3	2013	35,288,213.00	10,739,840.00	74,081,345.00	7,271,637.00	7,393,861.00	66,682,494.00	66,682,494.00	10,720,610.00	3,468,203.00	0.05	0.90	(0.14)	9.02	0.48	6.73	Safe	
3	2014	40,784,783.00	14,676,502.00	72,452,789.00	11,349,589.00	827,568.00	12,177,157.00	60,220,612.00	60,220,612.00	(5,592,304.00)	3,326,913.00	0.05	0.83	(0.08)	4.95	0.56	4.40	Safe
3	2015	50,533,071.00	33,603,871.00	88,553,116.00	30,502,911.00	4,402,168.00	34,905,079.00	53,643,237.00	53,643,237.00	(3,086,398.00)	3,100,980.00	0.04	0.61	(0.03)	1.54	0.58	2.27	Distress
3	2016	58,236,377.00	34,115,618.00	87,615,138.00	55,919,768.00	6,709,676.00	62,629,444.00	24,985,117.00	24,985,117.00	(19,789,847.00)	(21,900,000.00)	(0.23)	(0.08)	0.40	0.65	0.24	(0.58)	Distress
3	2017	69,065,240.00	32,671,569.00	88,898,991.00	97,467,795.00	5,352,184.00	103,400,000.00	(14,815,555.00)	(14,519,988.00)	(30,184,906.00)	(64,800,000.00)	(0.73)	(0.17)	(0.34)	(0.14)	0.78	(1.54)	Distress
3	2018	76,156,826.00	33,971,203.00	86,876,951.00	157,000,000.00	3,919,986.00	160,900,000.00	(71,170,461.00)	(40,567,573.00)	(123,000,000.00)	(142,000,000.00)	(1.42)	(0.82)	(0.48)	(0.46)	0.88	(3.82)	Distress
3	2019	60,604,365.00	47,465,190.00	102,500,000.00	44,514,222.00	5,775,257.00	50,289,679.00	51,964,988.00	52,164,988.00	132,000,000.00	0.01	0.51	1.29	1.04	0.79	6.38	Safe	
3	2020	38,807,144.00	103,700,000.00	171,000,000.00	102,600,000.00	4,488,290.00	107,100,000.00	(63,891,368.00)	(63,891,368.00)	6,312,633.00	1,033,283.00	0.01	0.37	0.04	0.60	0.58	1.59	Distress
3	2021	131,800,000.00	123,000,000.00	203,000,000.00	119,800,000.00	45,169,789.00	164,900,000.00	(57,997,268.00)	58,197,689.00	(1,316,911.00)	(6,000,000.00)	(0.65)	0.28	(0.10)	0.40	0.65	1.45	Distress
3	2022	137,400,000.00	105,200,000.00	217,000,000.00	117,300,000.00	45,116,413.00	162,400,000.00	(50,214,413.00)	160,700,000.00	(8,014,931.00)	(10,500,000.00)	(0.05)	0.23	(0.01)	0.54	0.63	(0.15)	Distress
3	2023	180,700,000.00	161,100,000.00	293,000,000.00	180,800,000.00	44,626,442.00	225,400,000.00	(67,364,832.00)	(67,564,850.00)	15,983,472.00	(19,700,000.00)	(0.07)	0.23	0.05	0.30	0.62	1.22	Distress
4	2013	37,843,503.00	8,040,322.00	46,860,525.00	2,938,758.00	3,160,632.00	6,099,390.00	40,756,135.00	40,756,135.00	(6,615,611.00)	5,101,564.00	0.11	0.87	(0.18)	6.68	0.81	5.56	Safe
4	2014	39,470,757.00	17,801,050.00	56,713,728.00	5,293,377.00	-	25,293,377.00	31,415,361.00	31,415,361.00	(9,340,784.00)	(7,492,327.00)	0.13	0.55	(0.16)	1.24	0.70	1.51	Distress
4	2015	45,681,614.00	28,599,947.00	67,017,585.00	43,547,365.00	18,476,797.00	62,024,162.00	4,988,423.00	4,988,423.00	(23,746,619.00)	(15,000,000.00)	(0.22)	0.07	(0.35)	0.08	0.68	(0.04)	Distress
4	2016	49,824,286.00	27,730,308.00	434,900,000.00	360,200,000.00	70,028,109.00	430,300,000.00	(62,933,598.00)	4,824,035.00	(11,986,612.00)	(133,000,000.00)	(0.31)	(0.12)	(0.03)	0.01	0.25	(0.37)	Distress
4	2017	59,696,060.00	63,165,255.00	103,700,000.00	136,600,000.00	17,701,755.00	154,300,000.00	(50,601,314.00)	(50,601,314.00)	(5,773,105.00)	(73,400,000.00)	(0.71)	(0.49)	(0.06)	(0.33)	0.58	(1.34)	Distress
4	2018	54,779,336.00	26,744,613.00	70,596,211.00	189,900,000.00	21,384,232.00	211,300,000.00	(140,700,000.00)	(140,700,000.00)	(32,411,612.00)	(163,000,000.00)	(2.31)	(1.99)	(0.46)	(0.67)	0.78	(6.70)	Distress
4	2019	57,232,407.00	31,514,251.00	77,128,621.00	261,700,000.00	20,732,133.00	282,400,000.00	(206,300,000.00)	(206,300,000.00)	(31,646,388.00)	(230,000,000.00)	(2.98)	(2.66)	(0.41)	(0.73)	0.74	(8.35)	Distress
4	2020	315,000,000.00	46,706,923.00	97,303,909.00	98,088,200.00	20,276,966.00	118,400,000.00	(27,065,857.00)	(27,065,857.00)	203,800,000.00	(53,000,000.00)	(0.58)	(0.30)	2.23	(0.23)	3.45	9.57	Safe
4	2021	183,800,000.00	69,680,523.00	105,000,000.00	119,800,000.00	45,169,789.00	164,900,000.00	(57,997,268.00)	58,197,689.00	(1,316,911.00)	(6,000,000.00)	(0.65)	0.28	(0.10)	0.40	0.65	1.45	Distress
4	2022	106,300,000.00	105,200,000.00	177,000,000.00	117,300,000.00	47,449,045.00	124,900,000.00	(50,214,413.00)	160,700,000.00	(8,014,931.00)	(1							

Company Representations

1. Abuja Electricity Distribution Company (AEDC) Plc
2. Benin Electricity Distribution Company (BEDC) Plc
3. Eko Electricity Distribution Company (EKEDC) Plc
4. Enugu Electricity Distribution Company (EEDC) Plc
5. Ibadan Electricity Distribution Company (IBEDC) Plc
6. Ikeja Electricity Distribution Company (IKEDC) Plc
7. Jos Electricity Distribution Company (JEDC) Plc
8. Kaduna Electricity Distribution Company (KAEDC) Plc
9. Kano Electricity Distribution Company (KEDC) Plc
10. Port Harcourt Electricity Distribution Company (PHEDC) Plc
11. Yola Electricity Distribution Company (YEDC) Plc

References

- 1) Abanihi, V. K., Ikheloa, S. O. & Okodede, F. (2018). Overview of the Nigerian power sector. *American Journal of Engineering Research*, 7(5), 253 – 263. www.ajer.org
- 2) Aideyan, D. O. (2023). Time series analysis of electricity generation in Nigeria from 1985 – 2014. *Journal of Science and Technology Research*, 5(2), 68-76. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8010065>.
- 3) Ajumogobia, H. & Okeke, C. (2015). Nigeria energy sector: legal and regulatory overview. Retrieved from www.ajumogobiaokeke.com.
- 4) Alastair, M. Claire, V. & Patricia, S. (2023). Predicting financial statement manipulation in South Africa: a comparison of the Beneish and Dechow models. *Cogent Economics & Finance*, 11(1), 1–33. doi: 10.1080/23322039.2023.2190215, <https://doi.org/10.1080/23322039.2023.2190215>.
- 5) Amaniyah, E., Mongid, A., Haryono, A. N., & Hariyati, H. (2025). Financial Distress Prediction Model, in C. D. M. Putri et al. (eds.), *Proceedings of the International Joint Conference on Arts and Humanities 2024 (IJCAH 2024)*, *Advances in Social Science, Education and Humanities Research* 879, 1695 – 1708. https://doi.org/10.2991/978-2-38476-317-7_160
- 6) Braunsberger, C., & Aschauer, E. (2025). Corporate failure prediction: a literature review of Altman Z-Score and Machine Learning Models within a technology adoption framework. *Journal of Risk and Financial Management*, 18(8), 465. <https://doi.org/10.3390/jrfm18080465>
- 7) Burnaby, P. A., Howe, M. A., & Muehlmann, B. (2011). Detecting fraud in the organization: an internal audit perspective. *Journal of Forensic & Investigative Accounting*, 3(1), 195–233.
- 8) Cindik, Z. & Armutlulu, I. H. (2021). A revision of the Altman Z-score model and a comparative analysis of Turkish companies' financial distress prediction. *National Accounting Review*, 3(2), 237–255. doi:10.3934/NAR.2021012.
- 9) Garcia, Y. & Esquivel, N. (2024). Evaluating financial distress risk: a comparative analysis using the Altman Z-score model. *Organization Development Journal*, 42(3). ISSN: 0889-6402 <http://odjournal.org/>

- 10) Gbadebo, A. D., Akande, J. O., & Adekunle, A. O. (2023). Financial statements fraud of banks and other financial institutions in Nigeria. *International Journal of Professional Business Review*, 8(9), 1-19. Doi: <https://doi.org/10.26668/businessreview/2023.v8i9.3074>
- 11) Hossain, D. A. (2020). Awareness towards forensic accounting and what non-accounting experts need to know. *International Journal of Science and Business*, 4(4), 128-143. doi: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3757586>.
- 12) Idris, A & Dzugwah, H. (2024). Corporate failure prediction tools: a comprehensive analysis of Altman Z-score and Argenti A-score models in financial distress assessment. *World Journal of Finance and Investment Research* 8(5). www.iiardjournals.org
- 13) Kamaluddin, A., Boni, L., Sutainim, A. N., & Mohammed, F. N. (2024). The relationship of Z-score and Beneish M-score: evidence from Malaysian Public Listed Companies. *Journal of Business and Social Development*, 12(2), 16–35. <http://doi.org/10.46754/jbsd.2024.09.002>
- 14) Kukreja, G., Gupta, M. S., Sarea, M. A. & Kumaraswamy, S. (2020). Beneish M-score and Altman Z-score as a catalyst for corporate fraud detection. *Journal of Investment Compliance*, 21(4), 231–241. doi:10.1108/joic.09.2020.0022.
- 15) Kulkarni, K. & Kothari, M. (2020). Altman’s Z-score model with selected financial indicators. *International Journal of Advances in Engineering and Management (IJAEM)*, 2(5), 419 – 425. doi: 10.35629;5252-02055419425.
- 16) Liodorova, J., Voronova, I. (2019). Z-score and P-score for bankruptcy fraud detection: a case of the construction sector in Latvia. *Contemporary Issues in Business, Management and Education*, 284-295. <https://doi.org/10.3846/cibmee.2019.029>.
- 17) MacCarthy, J. (2017). Using Altman Z-score and Beneish M-score models to detect financial fraud and corporate failure: a case study of Enron corporation. *International Journal of Finance and Accounting*, 6(6), 159–166. doi: 10.5923/j.ijfa.20170606.01,
- 18) Miharsi, D., Gamayuni, R. R., & Diharma, F. (2024). Analysis of the utilization of Altman Z-score, Beneish M-score, and F-score model in detecting fraudulent of financial reporting *Journal of Management, Accounting, General Finance and International Economic Issues (Marginal)*, 3(2), 353–363. <https://ojs.transpublika.com/index.php/MARGINAL/>.
- 19) Nyakarimi, S. (2022). Probable earning manipulation and fraud in banking sector: empirical study from east Africa. *Cogent Economics & Finance*. doi:10.2083477 <https://doi.108/23322039.2022.2083477>
- 20) Obiora, G. N., Igbinsosa, G. O., & Fiemobebeba, C. B. (2024). Technical losses across distribution networks in Nigeria and mitigative measures: a review. *ABUAD Journal of Engineering Research and Development (AJERD)*, 8(1), 43 – 49. <https://doi.org/10.53982/ajerd>
- 21) Okaro, S. C & Okafor, G. O. (2011). Creative accounting, corporate governance watchdog institutions, and systems: The case of Cadbury (Nig) Plc. Available at SSRN: <https://ssrn.com/abstract=1946441> or <http://dx.doi.org/10.2139/ssrn.1946441>
- 22) Okaro, S. C., Okafor, G. O. & Ofoegbu, G. (2013). Corporate fraud in Nigeria: A two-case study. *International Journal of Research in Management*, 6(3), 9–17.
- 23) Okiro, K. & Otiso, D. O. (2021). Detection of fraud in financial statements using Beneish ratios for companies listed at Nairobi Securities Exchange. *African Development Finance Journal*, 3(1), 92-126
- 24) Onyegbule, E. (2023). Making electricity reform work in developing economies. *Amazon Publishers*.

- 25) Pratiwi, A.S., Satoto, S. H., Wahyu, S. B., & Suprapti, S. (2022). The effect of financial ratio in the Altman Z-score on financial distress. *International Journal of Economics, Business and Accounting Research (IJEBAR)*, 6(1), 413–420. doi: 10.29040/ijebar.v6i1.4736
- 26) Ranjbar, S., & Amanollahi, G. F. (2018). The effect of financial distress on earnings management and unpredicted net earnings in companies listed on Tehran Stock Exchange. *Management Science Letters*, 8(9), 933-938. <https://doi.org/10.5267/j.msl.2018.6.015>
- 27) Rasa, K. & Zivile, G. (2015). The model of fraud detection in financial statements by means of financial ratios. *Procedia – Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 213, 321–327. doi: 10.1016/j.sbspro.2015.11.545
- Saleh, M. M. A., Aladwan, M., Alsingiawi, O., & Almari, M. O. S. (2021). Predicting fraudulent financial statements using fraud detection models. *Academy of Strategic Management*, 20(3), 1–17.
- 28) Singh, G. & Singla, R. (2023). Prediction of financial distress in the Indian corporate sector: an improvement over Altman's Z-score model. *International Journal of Business Continuity and Risk Management*, 13(1), 1–18. doi: 10.1504/IJBCRM.2023.10055472
- 29) Siregar, R., Lores, L., Sari, P. W., Sagala, C. I., & Saragih, F. (2023). The applicability of the Beneish M-score method for detecting financial statement fraud in manufacturing companies during the COVID-19 pandemic. *Journal of System and Management Sciences*, 13(6), 622–634. doi:10.33168/JSMS.2023.0636.
- 30) Teja, R. M (2025). Predicting bankruptcy and financial distress using Altman Z-score, Grover G-score, Springate S-score and Zmijewski X-score - a study on select companies. *Advances in Consumer Research*, 2(5), 494 - 500
- 31) Thomas, O. A., Rotimi, M. A., Franklin, C. M. & Tolulope, D. M. (2023). Evaluation of pre- and post-privatization of Nigeria's electric power system. *International Journal of Engineering Research Updates*, 34–41. Doi: <https://doi.org/1053430/Ijeru.2023.4.1.0018>.
- 32) Toly, A. A., Permatasari, R., & Wiranata, E. (2020). The effect of financial ratio (Altman Z-Score) on financial distress prediction in manufacturing sector in Indonesia 2016-2018. *Advances in Economics, Business and Management Research*, 144, 47 – 53. Doi:10.2991/aebmr.k.200606.008.